

ALTER-EGO: A mobile robot with functionally anthropomorphic upper body designed for physical interaction.

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Abstract—In this talk we present ALTER-EGO, an open-source mobile robot with a functionally anthropomorphic upper body, designed to operate in different environments, and equipped with soft robotics technologies to enable safe physical interactions with humans and the environment, to guarantee robustness and to allow versatility. ALTER-EGO is powered by Variable Stiffness Actuators and each arm mounts an anthropomorphic synergistically actuated artificial hand. The upper body is integrated with a two-wheels self-balancing mobile base to minimize the robot footprint and increase agility. ALTER-EGO features also sensors and a computational system which, together with a modular pilot station, make the robot able to function either autonomously or in an, optionally immersive, tele-operation mode. Finally, a plausible use case scenario - a robot avatar in a domestic environment - is described and investigated through a preliminary experimental session.

I. INTRODUCTION

Historically, robots found application mostly in factories and plants. Until recently, the most noticeable examples of robot systems directly sold to the consumer were limited to edutainment systems, automated chore robots, and social tele-presence platforms. Initially, all robots belonging to this latter category, consisted in a mobile base topped by an interactive screen. Nowadays, following a trend of anthropomorphization of technology, humanoid torsos are starting to replace those simple screens sharing the same social communication modalities of humans, e.g. body posture, gestures and facial expressions. On the other hand there are promising examples (e.g. Walkman [1]) of humanoid robots developed to operate in unstructured environments and perform challenging interaction tasks, e.g.: walk on rough terrains, move heavy objects, solve complex bi-manual manipulation tasks. One of the key aspects which led to the effectiveness of these robots was the use of enabling technologies capable to let the robots interact with the surrounding world, as e.g. active impedance control and series elastic actuation. Indeed, these same technologies are one of the main enablers that let robot arms cross the borders of industrial work cells, to become collaborative robots that can work in close contact with people and share the same operating space. It is in the opinion of the authors that the application of the same Soft Robotics technologies,

Fig. 1. ALTER-EGO, a soft dual-arm mobile platform equipped with variable stiffness actuation units and soft under-actuated hands.

which includes series elastic and variable impedance actuation, in a consumer-oriented scenario, together with the capillary diffusion of reliable and affordable computational, networking and sensing technologies, will enable the massive diffusion of a novel generation of robots capable to deal with challenges imposed by real world scenarios.

Inspired by DARPA Robotics Challenge (DRC)¹ and the more recent announcement of the ANA - Avatar XPRIZE (XP)², in this talk we present ALTER-EGO (Fig. 1), a robust and versatile mobile platform, capable to perform safe physical human-robot interactions and to operate in different working scenarios.

This talk is extracted from [2]. Most of the hardware and software technologies adopted, developed and explicitly designed for ALTER-EGO, are distributed under an open-source framework, and are available on the Natural Machine Motion Initiative website³ (NMMI).

II. ALTER-EGO

ALTER-EGO is powered by Variable Stiffness Actuators (VSA). Moreover, each of its arms mounts an anthropo-

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¹<https://www.darpa.mil/program/darpa-robotics-challenge>

²<https://avatar.xprize.org/prizes/avatar>

³www.naturalmachinemotioninitiative.com

Fig. 2. ALTER-EGO used in immersive tele-operation mode operating in a domestic environment. The pilot station is composed by wearable devices like Oculus Rift and MYO armbands. In (a), the robot is used to prepare food for pets. In (b) a box is retrieved from a mail man using the robot.

morphic synergistic artificial hand inspired by the human motor synergies. The upper body is mounted on a two-wheels self-balancing mobile base to minimize the robot footprint and increase agility. ALTER-EGO can be used also in tele-operation. In particular, when used in combination with a pilot station mainly composed of lightweight and wearable Input/Output devices, the system features an immersive control mode. This modality, when combined with the use of Tele-Impedance control [3], is able to match the pilot and robot mechanical behavior, not only in terms of movements, but also in terms of mechanical impedance, as derived from the user muscle activation.

III. ROBOT AVATAR IN A DOMESTIC ENVIRONMENT

Fig.2 shows ALTER-EGO operating in a domestic use-case scenario. Action showed are mostly executed with the immersive tele-operation operating mode, envisioning that an hypothetical user can jump inside the robot from its work location and teleport himself at home to assolve some domestic tasks. In Fig.2(a), the pilot use the robot to prepare food for a pet. In Fig.2(b), a mail man is delivering an object to the pilot house. In this circumstance the operator use ALTER-EGO to pick up a credit card, retrieve the box from the mail man, pay, and come back to the house. The experimental activity was performed from two different locations posed at a distance of five kilometers (pilot station placed at the Engineering building of the University of Pisa). Although not exhaustive

such experience demonstrate the potential and effectiveness of the approach.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this talk we presented ALTER-EGO, a dual-arms mobile platform developed whit soft robotic technologies both for the actuation and manipulation layer. Features resulting from this kind of technologies, like flexibility, adaptivity and robustness allow ALTER-EGO to interact with environment and objects, as well as allow to improve safety when the robot is in action around humans.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Authors would like to thank Cristiano Petrocelli, Gaspare Santaera, Mattia Poggiani, Michele Maimeri, Manuel Barbarossa, Vinicio Tincani, and Ashwin Vasudevan for their work on the design and implementation of the ALTER-EGO robot. Grazia Zambella, Alessandro Palleschi, and Luca Bonamini, for their help in the experimental activities.

REFERENCES

- [1] Negrello, Francesca, et al. "Humanoids at work: The walk-man robot in a postearthquake scenario." *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine* 25.3 (2018): 8-22.
- [2] Lentini, Gianluca, et al. "ALTER-EGO: A mobile robot with functionally anthropomorphic upper body designed for physical interaction." *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine* (under review)
- [3] Ajoudani, Arash, Nikos Tsagarakis, and Antonio Bicchi. "Tele-impedance: Teleoperation with impedance regulation using a body-machine interface." *The International Journal of Robotics Research* 31.13 (2012): 1642-1656.